

Examining the Effect of Exchange Rate Volatility on Foreign Investors Buying Real Estate from Turkey

Dr. Tughan TURAN

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Abstract

In our nation, studies in legal research on the acquisition of real estate by foreigners often begin with a discussion of the subject's history and at some time in the work, the concept of surrender is brought up. In some of the legal studies that have been done on the matter, the idea of capitulation has also been mentioned. It's possible that at various points in the continuing debates, this concept will be brought to the front. When governments enact laws to attract foreigners to buy real estate in Turkey, criticism may surface with headlines like "Like Capitulations" or something like. These policies are intended to attract foreigners to invest in Turkish real estate. These limitations were put in place to entice actual people who are now living in other nations to visit Turkey and purchase real estate there. It is essential to begin with capitulations because they are an idea that never goes out of style, they are connected to foreigners buying property in Turkey, they occurred during the fall of the Ottoman Empire, and they formed Turkey. The laws of the state in which the individual lives and of which they are a citizen are enforced by this contract. Both a temporary and permanent migration may occur. According to Zürcher, non-Muslim Christians who lived in the Ottoman Empire were bound to follow Islamic law since they were governed by the Eman system, which was founded on the legal precepts of Islamic law. The tenets of Islamic law were used to build the Eman system. The ambassadors and consuls of the state of which they are citizens have been given certain discretion in affairs and activities taking place inside the communities they are. This independence had to do with problems and occurrences in the areas they oversaw representing. This autonomy included dealing with issues that developed not just in their local community but also in the state. This article investigates how currency changes affect international buyers buying Turkish real estate.

Keywords: *Exchange Rate Mobility, Foreigners Buying Real Estate from Turkey, Foreign Investors Buying Real Estate, The Effect of Exchange Rate on Real Estate*

1. Introduction

Throughout the history of the nation, several legal laws governing the rights and duties of foreign national real and legal persons in the purchase of real estate in Turkey have been created, subject to change and development. The purpose of this Regulation is to set out the rights and responsibilities of foreign natural and legal persons buying real estate on national territory.

The regulations apply to the purchase of real estate that is situated within the boundaries of this nation. These rules lay out the steps that must be taken to buy property within the nation's boundaries. Nowadays, attempts are undertaken to reduce these barriers within the confines of certain principles, particularly considering the impact of globalization and the shift to an economy based on free market principles. The fact that there are more people on the planet than ever before makes these efforts possible. Several fundamental notions have been developed as a consequence of these efforts, making them adaptable. A handful of these states recently implemented legislation making it unlawful for non-citizens to have property inside their boundaries, which was formerly allowed.

Non-citizens are prohibited from buying real estate because of these regulations. The existing legislative framework that regulates the procedure for foreigners to buy property in Turkey has developed over time and therefore has grown more unpredictable and complex. I started my investigation by creating a broad framework for the subject at hand. A complete framework has also been created. First, a search in the relevant literature was conducted. Next, the internet and library resources were searched for related publications. Third, the procedure was finished by using the chosen resources. This was done to kick off the conceptual framework creation process.

An overview of the historical process for foreign natural and legal people buying real estate is also included. Then, we examine these different systems by contrasting and comparing them to the national program. The last section of my paper focuses on the challenges that foreign real and legal persons have when trying to buy real estate. Additionally, the subject was broken down according to how it affected the legal system, and oral interviews with different practitioners were undertaken. His opinions on issue identification and potential remedies were taken into consideration. The study spans many topics. Because its main goal is to find the challenges faced by actual or legitimate foreign organizations trying to purchase real estate in another nation, as well as the effects of exchange rate mobility on international investors purchasing real estate from Turkey. Additionally, it shows that he researches a variety of topics. Therefore, rather than outlining the issues in great detail, solutions are proposed by focusing

on the challenges that are often experienced in practice. To reduce the chance of overlooking any potential problems, this is done.

In Turkey, it is customary to leave this criteria out of both the laws governing citizenship and the administration of civil law. The primary cause of this predicament is the absence of a specific provision in Turkish law that governs the law applicable to foreigners. There are a few significant exceptions to this accepted norm, however, that you should be aware of. To assess whether the subject is a foreign national or not, the subject is compared across two distinct groups, natural people and legal organizations. Foreign natural person: Although they are regarded as people, instances of foreign legal entities include people, governments, organizations, and businesses (The Concept of Foreigner in terms of Real and Legal Persons). In some respects, the procedure for determining a natural person's or legal entity's citizenship is comparable to the procedure for determining a person's foreign qualification. In other words, one must first understand what the term "citizen" implies in order to comprehend who a "non-citizen" is (Tekinalp, 2003:6). At its convention in 1892, the State Law Institute supplied the following definition of the foreigner:

"A person who is in the territory of a state but does not have the right to claim the citizenship of that state" (Levi, 2006: 17)

In Turkey, a person is considered to be a "foreigner" if they do not have any citizenship links with the Republic of Turkey, as stated in Article 2 of the Turkish Citizenship Law No. 5901. This stipulation may be found in the legal document (See RG. T. 12.06.2009 P.27256). The text of this Act is available for perusal in the Official Gazette (RG. T. 12.06.2009 p.27256). To put it another way, a person might be seen as a foreigner even though he or she may be a citizen of another state, a non-state person, or a refugee. The term "foreigner" may be used to each of these diverse types of people. This is due to the fact that just holding the citizenship of another country does not exclude a person from being considered a "foreigner" (Altuğ, 1976:8). As can be seen from these definitions, some people decide who is foreign based on the criterion of being different in terms of status, while others determine who is foreign based on the criteria of citizenship.

Both criteria for defining who belongs in the category of a foreigner are acceptable approaches to the problem of classifying people. Some individuals decide if another individual is a foreigner based on whether or not they are in a different position, while others decide whether or not a person is a citizen of a given nation based on whether or not they are a citizen of that country. An example of a definition that views the foreigner in terms of the legal situation to

which he or she is subject might be provided this viewpoint, which claims that the individual obtains the foreign character owing to his position. One example of a definition that considers the location of the stranger is the one shown below. Specifically, this approach states that the fundamental factor that defines whether a person is considered a foreigner is their status in society. One may also say that a definition is formed from the rights that are granted to immigrants. This is another way of putting the idea. This is another meaning that may be derived from the phrase.

2. The Word "Stranger"

People who arrived in the nation very recently from other countries People who arrived in the nation very recently from other countries In light of these many understandings of the term "foreigner," we can classify those who fit into this group according to the subcategories that are listed below. In this scenario, a person is regarded a foreigner in the broadest and most all-encompassing meaning imaginable if they have a true link of nationality that binds them to one or more states. This applies even if they have dual or many nationalities. This definition applies to a person no matter how many different nations they have, regardless of if they just have one. This is since the context permits such a meaning. In this unique circumstance, the individual in question is regarded as a foreigner not only about the state or states of which he holds citizenship, but also with regard to every other state. This is the case because of the exceptional circumstances surrounding this situation. It makes no difference whether you are a citizen of one of these states or not; this is the case in any instance. This is because the individual in issue has no nationality in any of the other states. (Levi, 2006: 19).

This decision was taken after taking into consideration the recommendations of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs as well as the views expressed by the other relevant ministries. The law divided each immigrant into one of four groups based on the traits that set them different from the others.

3. Categorizing the Real Estate Desired to Buy According to the Criteria

It's possible for one section of our nation to have economic circumstances, cultural norms, physical environment, and climatic patterns that are substantially different from those of another location in our country. Therefore, it is of major significance to pick the place and location that you will discover the most appropriate attributes. The piece of real estate that you are interested in purchasing must be classified in accordance with the criteria that you desire,

and it must also be able to satisfy both your requirements and your expectations for this classification to be regarded as acceptable. Before opting to buy the property in issue, it is strongly advisable to visit the property in question in order to properly evaluate the various possibilities accessible. The legal, physical, and financial status of the real estate that is being considered for purchase, as well as the fact that it has been internationally appraised by a real estate appraisal firm that is authorized by both the Capital Markets Board (CMB) and the Banking Regulation and Supervision Agency, are the most important issues that need to be considered in this particular scenario. In addition, the property in question has been internationally appraised by a real estate appraisal firm. In addition to this, the international value that was created by a real estate assessment business that is accredited by both the Capital Markets Board (CMB) and the Banking Regulation and Supervision Agency should also be taken into consideration.

An international value will be assigned to a real estate assessment firm that has been granted approval by both the Capital Markets Board (CMB) and the Banking Regulation and Supervision Agency. This should be done in combination with the local valuation (BDDK) (BDDK). The Valuation Report that has been developed by the requirements have to be used so that there is no room for compromise in any manner. The relevant legislation demands reporting of value and gives confidence that the amount you will pay, and your rights will be safeguarded inside the system. Briefly, following this provision of the law becomes a mandatory requirement. You need to guarantee that all your company operations are done inside a dependable, clear and impartial legal framework. To do this, you will need to confer with industry professionals who are specialists. Collaborating with many other specialists in the area is one technique to reach this aim.

Real estate investing in Turkey has been recognized as both the most trustworthy and the safest sort of investment for a long time. This is since the value of these assets continues to increase while simultaneously supplying a consistent income. This is because the value of these assets normally grows as time goes. Because of this feature, buying and selling real estate will not produce any loss of value for you in terms of the subject item. With its higher rental status according to its purpose and location, with a more stable income, with agreements agreed upon based on the concept of mutual benefit, and with the potential to buy citizenship by purchasing property as the last step, the property offers more advantages than other cities in terms of cost, quality, and living standards. It is essential to be in the right posture. As a direct consequence of the changes that are taking place, it is now necessary to decide whether individuals living in specific nations have access to alternatives to lifestyles that are not only appealing but also high

in quality when compared to those living in other countries. In contrast, those who live in other nations don't have these rights.

Real estate is an essential part of a sound financial system since it may be used to secure loans and other obligations. The fact that the real estate may be used as collateral is the explanation for this situation. Turkey is well placed in a sector of the global economy that is experiencing remarkable progress in a broad range of investment industries, and the investment sector that has seen the most substantial growth is the tourist investment sector. Its geographical position, which makes it the focus of attention owing to its extraordinarily distinctive culture, is a crossing place between Asia and Europe, and has both finished and continuing mega projects . It is the focus of everyone's attention because of its geographical position, which in turn makes it the focus of everyone's attention because of its very distinctive culture.

These choices include a wide array of architectural styles that are eye-catching in appearance and very innovative in terms of the technological capabilities they provide. According to Bekmez-Ozpolat (2013), the housing market is an incredibly important sector not only because it satisfies the need for shelter, which is a fundamental human right, but also because it has a considerable influence on GDP through influencing many other industries that are interrelated. Because the need for shelter is a fundamental human right. In addition, housing is a highly significant sector in terms of satisfying the demand for shelter, which is a fundamental human right. This is because having a secure place to sleep is a fundamental human right. In addition, the provision of shelter as a service satisfies the need for a location in which to seek refuge from the elements. According to Arthur O'Sullivan, the traits that separate housing from other industries include the variability of the housing stock, defined by durable but wearable housing, and, of course, pricey housing.

These characteristics, when combined, set the housing industry apart from other sectors (2011). There are a few components of the housing industry that manage the comparatively high costs associated with it when compared to the costs of other industries. Another trait that separates real estate from other assets is that it may be subject to many different transactions. This feature makes real estate a pricey investment. When taken in conjunction with the total revenue of the country, real estate is sometimes seen as a potential for investment. The housing market is controlled by a system that is governed by supply and demand, and the individual spending habits of consumers have a substantial influence on this mechanism in several different ways. The need for a place to live is no longer restricted to the people of a single country as a direct consequence of the dissolution of legal borders brought about by the expansion of globalization. This transformation took place as a direct consequence of the consequences that

globalization has had. Although the procedure of selling real estate to foreign citizens or foreign legal firms resident in the country is similar in most countries throughout the globe, there are some significant differences. There are certain nations that do not allow the selling of residential properties to citizens of other nations, while others do. In the context of direct foreign capital, the sale of real estate to individuals from other countries results in an influx of foreign currency into the country. Therefore, nations that struggle to give a current account deficit try to revitalize their economies by imposing a variety of regulations on the real estate market. The reason for this is that the purchase of real estate by individuals from other countries results in an influx of foreign currency into the nation. This is since the transaction of real estate to persons residing in other nations results in the entry of that nation's economy into possession of foreign money. The most prominent example of this technique is purposely weakening a country's currency to achieve a price competitive edge in the market. This strategy is used to get a competitive edge in terms of pricing. In addition, to entice foreign direct investment, certain nations' governments are investigating the feasibility of presenting citizenship to non-citizens who have made substantial financial investments in the nation's real estate market. This is done with the intention of boosting the number of persons who are not originally from the nationality buying real estate in the country. Real estate may be sold to non-citizens in several countries, including France, the Netherlands, and Germany, in exchange for a direct investment amount or without any limitations at all, such as a required length of time spent living in the nation by the purchaser.

Different nations have different laws about the legality of this activity. Real estate transactions may be completed in some nations, including the United Kingdom, Australia, and China, in return for the appropriate amount of investment financial contribution from the buyer or if the buyer satisfies the terms of ownership in the property. The sale of residential property to non-natives is influenced by a broad variety of factors, such as the location of the property geographically, its asking price, the applicable tax laws, and regulations, as well as the economics, policies, and national security of the country in question.

There is a significant role that real estate transactions play in Turkey's overall economic environment. These transactions are particularly significant when they include the selling of property to purchasers found in other countries. This is particularly important to keep in mind while doing business involving the selling of real estate to purchasers situated in other countries. According to the figures on house sales compiled by TUIK in April 2022, the proportion of homes sold to foreign purchasers as a percentage of total sales reached 4.8 percent. This number was generated from the fact that the proportion of residences sold to

foreign purchasers grew as a percentage of overall sales. These findings are predicated on the observation that a growing proportion of the total number of homes bought and sold are closed deals with purchasers who live in countries other than the United States. The results of the same poll show that between the months of January and April, there was a rise of 48.9 percent in the number of individuals living in other countries who were interested in purchasing property in the United States. These persons are considered to have purchasing power for a property. This study's aim is to analyze the factors—including housing price index and exchange rate fluctuations—that influence the number of homes that are sold to individuals of various nationalities all over the globe.

The hypothesis in this study is that there would be a rise in the housing demand of overseas purchasers in Turkey because of the increase in the real effective exchange rate, commonly known as the real appreciation of the lira. This estimate was examined with the presumption that there would be an inverse correlation between these two aspects, and this hypothesis was evaluated. This estimate also requires testing with the premise that there will be inverse correlation between the two variables in issue.

The study sheds light on the foreign housing demand in Turkey as well as the variables that are influencing it. In summing up, the study presents a comprehensive review of empirical investigations that are associated with this subject matter. It supplies an explanation of the model that was used in the study, in addition to the estimate outcomes that were produced.

The will of persons from other nations to own property may be affected by a range of situations, such as political connections, economic conditions, geographic location, familial limits and legal requirements.

4. Significant Effect of Difference in Exchange Rates on Price

This mismatch is by far the most important of the three since the difference in currency rates has a substantial impact on the pricing. When one nation's currency appreciates in value in comparison to the currency of another nation, this has the effect of driving down the cost of real estate in the second nation. This occurs because the worth of a nation's currency in comparison to the currency of another nation has an effect on the price of a product in the other nation. According to Asal (2018), the rise in the exchange rate entices international purchasers to the country and proves that consumers who can pay in foreign currency are able to acquire real estate. The rise in the currency's value also encourages shoppers from other countries to go to the country to make purchases. This is the situation since it sends the message that customers are in a position to acquire properties throughout the country. In addition, migration,

which happens because of the rise in human mobility that occurs as a result of the changes in political, social, and economic situations, contributes to the need for housing of persons who are not citizens of the nation where the movement is taking place. Migration has led to an increase in human mobility, which in turn has led to a rise in the need for housing. Migration has an effect not only on the demand for housing but also on the price of housing, according to Saiz (2007). In other words, migration has an influence that is both positive and negative. In the same way, variables such as geographical closeness, religious and cultural similarity, cultural similarity, the view of cities as a healthy and living place, and the impression of limited geopolitical hazards all contribute to the rise in the desire to own property in another country. These are all aspects that have a role in the rising interest in buying real estate in another country. Another element that might influence the real estate market among purchasers from other nations is the tax regulations. It's possible that this aspect plays a role as well. According to Gorcack and Keys's (2020) interpretation, the principal aim of imposing house taxes on foreign purchasers was to halt the inflow of capital from other nations and to maintain the integrity of the real estate market.

Non-citizens are allowed the right to buy immovables, if they follow all legal constraints and are in reciprocity with the people of the nation where the immovable is situated, as stated in Article 35 of the Constitution. This privilege is provided to non-citizens on the condition that they see all the legal constraints that apply to them. This right is provided to them on condition that they jointly cooperate with the citizens of the country in which the property is situated. One of the few modifications that have been made during this legislation's existence is the most recent alteration, which took place in 2012 when Law No. 6302 was approved as the new law. The concept of reciprocity no longer applies because of an adjustment that was enacted on May 18, 2012, under Article 35 of Law No. 6302 of Land Registry Law No. 2644. (Official Gazette, 2012).

Also, non-Turkish people may buy jeans from Turkey if they satisfy the proper legal conditions. One cannot make such a statement about those who were born and brought up in Turkey. The proper Ministries must supply their stamp of approval to the plans before they can be conducted on the piece of property that they have bought within a time frame of two years. Özdemir (2018) says that as a direct consequence of these adjustments made in the name of house purchase, 183 countries have been awarded privileges within legal boundaries. These modifications were done to lower the overall cost of buying a property. This whole operation was conducted under the premise of buying a home. It is now possible for a foreign investor to become a citizen of the Republic of Turkey according to Law No. 30540, which was passed on

September 19, 2018. This law made it permissible for international investors to apply for Turkish citizenship. As a result of this amendment, a foreign investor can qualify for citizenship in the Republic of Turkey if he or she owns real estate with a value of 250 thousand dollars rather than 1 million dollars and agrees not to sell that real estate for a period of three years. In addition, the investor must pledge not to sell the real estate during that period.

According to the conclusions of the study done by Emlak Konut GYO A, (2018), the reason for such significant interest in Istanbul is because it is viewed as the most urbanized city in the world. Simply said, Istanbul has a higher population density than any other metropolis in the world.

The reputation of Antalya as a city that focuses largely on servicing tourists substantially impacts the decisions that visitors from other countries make in the city. 2018 was the year in which the most residences were sold to non-nationals in Bursa.

The acquisition of 2,720 houses and condominiums in and around the city made this feat possible. The provinces of Istanbul, Antalya, Bursa, Ankara, Aydın, and Muğla are often considered to be the most desirable options. The ease of transit in these provinces, the steps that have been taken to enhance the infrastructure, and the projects that have been conducted to generate excellent housing have all contributed to a growth in interest in these places.

It is possible to find a variety of research on housing demand and the macroeconomic variables that affect housing demand in the body of scholarly work that has been published. These studies investigate a broad variety of subject areas. This research examines the housing demand not only in Turkey but also in other nations across the globe. Because there hasn't been a lot of study carried out on the topic, not a lot of attention has been paid to the factors that could explain why people of different nationalities are considering buying property in Turkey. This aim will be carried out by integrating in this article not only research on the housing demand in Turkey but also research on the housing demand in other nations. Within this area of the construction business, one can also find studies on the housing demand in a variety of nations. According to the findings of research conducted by Lu Han (2010), it is expected that homeowners would adopt a pattern of sparse and dynamic house purchase in the future. This study also investigates the impact that the danger of rising housing prices has on the demand for homes. It has been shown that the dispersal of financial incentives results in a decrease in the present demand for housing, which, in turn, results in a decrease in the financial risk that families will face in the future. This is a kind of consciousness that is followed, and it is followed effectively. Researchers Stepanyan, Poghosyan, and Bibolov (2010) employed panel data econometrics in their study to detect the cycle of decline and boom in real estate markets

in certain nations that were once a part of the Soviet Union. These countries include Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Belarus. Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Moldova, and Ukraine are the names of the nations in question. Several nations, including Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, and Kazakhstan, are examples of those that are included in this group. During times of widespread economic instability, it was discovered that both the total quantity of foreign money held as well as the number of foreign investments suffered significant losses. It turned out that this was the case for both factors. After further investigation, it was found that this was, in fact, the situation. Liu Yachen and Zhang Shuai (2013) adopted the causality approach as the study technique to explore the link between China's exchange rate and real estate values. Their investigation was aimed at deciding whether there was a correlation between the two. The purpose of the research was to evaluate the impact that changing one element had on another. Cointegration is another term for the relationship that has been shown to exist between the value of the housing stock in a nation and the exchange rate of that country during the last several years. This connection has been proved to exist.

In their study that was released in 2014, Oktay, Karaaslan, and Alkan analyze the factors that affect the demand for housing in Turkey from several different perspectives. These components manage defining the variables that manage deciding what factors manage deciding the demand for housing. Karasu (2015) conducted research to decide whether a bubble existed in the real estate market in Turkey during the time under investigation. In addition to this, he used time series analysis to understand the dynamics of the connection that exists between the myriad of elements that influence property values and the prices themselves. It is reasonable to assume that 2012 will be remembered as the year that marked the beginning of the most recent period of expansion. This is a finding that is up for discussion and analysis. Ceritoğlu (2017) conducted research to decide how the real estate bubble in Turkey affects the distribution of wealth according to ownership status. Using information gathered from surveys of household budgets, he was able to do this. It has been shown that money is the single most significant element that plays an equally vital influence in shaping housing demand as does house ownership. Kangall Uyar and Kılıç (2017) used spatial econometric models in their study for their paper to examine the impacts of space effect on house sales at the regional level. This was done to write about their findings. It has become known that the Durbin Model is the one that supplies the most correct explanation of the link between the variables affecting housing demand on a regional scale and the demand for housing. This was achieved by setting up that the model supplied the best correct description of the connection between the two entities. This conclusion was arrived at because of the results after it was set up that the model gave the most

correct explanation. Using the WEKA program, Onder and Turgut (2018) studied the factors that influence the demand for rental housing among households, as well as the data that was acquired from the survey of household budgets. In addition to this, they investigated how each of these aspects influenced the budget for the home. This study looked at the factors that drive the demand for rental housing among families, with a particular emphasis on the demand among families for rental accommodation. According to this conclusion, there is a connection between the worth of the house as an investment property and other aspects of the home's value. This finding also shows that there is a connection between the two values. It has been discovered that the worth of the house in terms of its potential as an investment property is connected to the value of the home in terms of its other qualities.

The S.W.O.T. approach was used by Çelik and Kral (2018) to conduct research on the elements that influence the housing demand in Turkey. In addition, methodologies for panel data analysis and methods for clustering were used in the investigation of the elements that play a role in determining the quantity of real estate transactions that take place in international markets. According to the findings of the study, each of the elements that were taken into consideration had some sort of an effect on the market for residential real estate. Panel Granger causality analysis was used in the study that was conducted by Mohsen Bahmani-Oskooee and Tsung-Pao Wu (2018) to analyze the link between prices in the housing market and foreign currency markets in terms of 18 OECD nations. However, despite positive and statistically significant findings for GDP per capita, inflation, share of elderly population aged 15-64, GDP growth rate, large money, and real exchange rate, it was discovered that house prices were high. This was the case even though GDP per capita, inflation, share of elderly population aged 15-64, and GDP growth rate were all found to be positive. Even if the GDP per capita, inflation, proportion of old population aged 15-64, wide currency, and real exchange rate were all judged to be positive, this was still the case. On the other hand, it was discovered that real interest rates had absolutely no impact whatsoever on the result of the experiment. This was in sharp contrast to the employment variable, which was shown to have a significant impact on the result of the research study. The authors Farhad Taghizadeh-Hesary, Naoyuki Yoshino, and Alvin Chiu (2019) conducted study on the major developments that are impacting the cost of housing in China. They found that these adjustments were induced by a range of variables and that these fundamental changes had an influence on the cost of housing. They also found that these shifts had an impact on the availability of housing.

It has been shown that one of the elements that contributes to the consolidation of price trends over time is the degree of variability in the housing price index variable. This is only one of

the aspects that helps to combine price patterns over time. Davarcıoğlu Özaktaş (2019) did research to set up to what degree the actual effective exchange rate influences the demand for real estate in Turkey in terms of international purchasers. The study was done to address the following question: It has been shown that a rise in the real effective exchange rate has a beneficial influence on the number of homes that overseas purchasers want to purchase. This was discovered via an analysis of data gathered from a wide variety of nations found all around the globe. Panel regression was used in the research undertaken by Anıl Ari, Damien Puy and Yu Shi (2020) to analyze the influence of shocks in foreign demand on home prices in the local region. In this specific research, monthly property prices in US postal codes serve as the dependent variable, while house price shocks serve as the independent variable. It was discovered, in the wake of the political crisis that occurred in other nations, that housing prices were rising at an abnormally high rate in certain regions of the United States. These regions were the ones with the highest population density of people who were originally from countries that were affected by the crisis.

5. The Effect of Exchange Rate Changes on Home Sales

The first step in researching the influence that shifts in exchange rates have on real estate sales was to investigate the part that shifts in exchange rates play in the transaction that takes place when residences are sold to persons who reside in other countries. This was done to aid with that, and it was done so that the impact of currency changes could be seen more clearly. In addition to that, something was done to make the other thing possible. During their investigation, the authors of the paper resorted to monthly statistics, numbers for total house sales for the period 2015-2021, the home price index, and the actual exchange rate. To begin, a unit root test with structural break was conducted in order to explore the kind of connection that exists between the two as well as the path that the connection points take. This was done so that we might get further information on the structural break that the link refers to. This was done to determine whether or not the two had any kind of connection, and the findings of the inquiry are shown down below. The findings of the Zivot-Andrews structural break unit root test showed that the variables of house sales to foreigners, real effective exchange rate, and house price index were stationary at the initial difference values. This conclusion was reached because of the fact that these three variables all shared the same initial difference value. This was the conclusion that could be drawn from the evidence that was found.

After the break unit root test was finished, the Gregory Hansen structural break cointegration test was carried out to determine whether or not the variables were in fact consistently

associated across time. Following the conclusion of the break unit root test, this next action was carried out. In the fixed interest (C) and regime change (C/S) model, there is a long-term cointegration link between house sales to foreigners, the housing price index, and real effective exchange rate variables. This relationship exists between the three variables. The Gregory-Hansen structural break cointegration test is one example of this kind of analysis. The Gregory-Hansen structural break cointegration model was analyzed, and the conclusions that were achieved from doing so are presented here. The results that were obtained via the Gregory-Hansen structural break cointegration test were directly responsible for making this discovery feasible. This was done so that we could obtain a better sense of the nature of the link once it had been established over a longer length of time. This tactic calls for the incorporation of structural breaks into the model and makes use of a dummy variable as a component of its overall implementation.

According to the results of the study, there is a fall of 3.4% in the number of homes that are sold to individuals originating from countries other than the United States whenever there is a 1% rise in the real effective exchange rate. This trend remains unchanged even after taking into account the true effective exchange rate, which may be either positive or negative. If there is a rise in the real effective exchange rate, the value of a country's currency will go down, but it will go up if there is a fall in the real effective exchange rate. On the other side, a rise in the real effective exchange rate will lead to an increase in the value of a country's currency. This is because of the positive feedback loop that exists between the two. This is due to the fact that the two elements have a cumulative influence on one another. The findings of the study indicate that the effect of the theoretically analyzed real exchange rate on house sales to foreigners is as follows: as the real effective exchange rate decreases (the national currency depreciates), the decrease in foreign currency housing prices increases the demand. This is the effect of the theoretically analyzed real exchange rate on house sales to foreigners.

When looking at the actual exchange rate and how it affects property sales to overseas purchasers, this is the hypothetical influence that the real exchange rate has on house sales to foreigners that is being studied. This study proves that the hypotheses that were formed before to the inquiry are valid, which supports the hypotheses that were made. It is consistent with the findings obtained from the research, which points to a positive relationship between exchange rate fluctuations and real estate sales to foreigners, as in the studies conducted by Davarcioglu and Ozaktaş. These findings point to a positive relationship between exchange rate fluctuations and real estate sales to foreigners. It is also consistent with the results of the study that showed a favorable association between exchange rate mobility and sales of real estate to domestic

purchasers. This conclusion is supported by the research. It is also consistent with the findings of the research, which showed a positive correlation between fluctuations in the value of the currency exchange rate and sales of real estate to purchasers from inside the country (2019). There has been a rise in the number of homes sold to individuals from other countries, particularly over the course of the last several years, as the consequence of the volatility in exchange rates. Because of this, it was discovered that Turkey brought in more money than its nation's currency could buy. In addition to this, there has been a rise for real estate that has been sold to people who are citizens of other nations. The most contentious and divisive aspect of this expansion, in many's eyes, is the rise in the number of persons who look for citizenship in return for housing. This is the most problematic aspect of this expansion. This expansion may be ascribed to several different sources. According to the results of our study, the policy of giving citizenship in return for property purchase in 2018 did not create a statistically significant decline in the number of house sales. This conclusion was reached after analyzing the data collected. This was the conclusion that was reached based on the data that was acquired while we were doing our investigation. This was the conclusion that could be drawn from the data that was gathered over the course of our investigation. When it comes to real estate in other nations, the value of the local currency has the largest impact on the decisions that prospective purchasers make. This is because of the higher cost of living in such countries. There has been a rise in the number of persons who wish to buy real estate in Turkey from other countries as a direct consequence of the devaluation of the Turkish lira in comparison to other currencies.

It is possible that avoiding an excessive rise in the value of the exchange rate would have the impact of decreasing demand for real estate among purchasers from other nations. It is quite probable that this impact will have a negative effect. It is possible that the difficulties that have been afflicting the real estate market would be alleviated and the amount of demand from purchasers based outside of Turkey will decrease if the value of the Turkish lira is permitted to increase to a greater level. Both in terms of the structure of the market and the conduct of its participants, the present status of the housing market has a substantial influence on a number of macroeconomic indicators. This is the case when considering both aspects of the market. This is true for both the supply and demand sides of the market. Within the context of macroeconomic theory, the significance of real estate as a place to live has surpassed that of real estate as an investment as a result of developments such as the expansion of the housing market and the development of the mortgage market. Although housing expenditures are classed as investment expenditures within the framework of macroeconomic theory, the

significance of housing has expanded so much that it can no longer be appropriately viewed as an investment. To provide more clarity, the dynamics of the housing market over the last many years have a complex structure that has the potential to cause catastrophes on a worldwide scale. This likelihood is owing to the fact that the housing market is now undergoing a boom. These aspects had a role in the rise in the number of properties that went into foreclosure and were subsequently sold in short deals.

In the empirical research, the long-term and short-term correlations, as well as the causality between the variables, between the Turkish lira exchange rate and the total number of properties sold to foreign purchasers in Turkey were analyzed. Also investigated was the link between the two variables. In addition, the research investigated the chain of events that occurred between the varied factors. Another aspect of the real estate market in Turkey that was investigated as part of this study was the total number of homes that were sold to foreign purchasers. Shelter, who may be regarded to be one of the most fundamental need for human existence, satisfies this requirement together with the want for a secure place to take refuge. When compared to other product and consumer goods categories in terms of price, it is undeniable that housing is the most important financial obligation for families (Coşkun, 2016:125). When people buy a home, a significant amount of the anxiety they have for their own safety in the future is alleviated. When considering the variables that contribute to the need for housing in general, human desire and the current economic condition stand out as the most significant contributors to this demand. When viewed in the broader context of the economy, a number of crucial factors, such as the quantity of money that is presently in circulation and the country's monetary policy, have a substantial impact on the demand for housing. This is since a rise in the total quantity of money in circulation results in a higher level of overall housing demand. Because of this, there is an increase in the demand for residential real estate. The current interest rate that lenders are offering is one of the variables that should be taken into profoundly serious account by persons who are attempting to determine whether or not they want to purchase a property. In other words, it is reasonable to expect that there will be a decline in the demand for housing whenever interest rates rise, and that there would be an increase in the demand for housing whenever interest rates fall (Badurlar, 2008:224). This is because the rate of return has a vital effect in deciding whether to invest one's money in saving or investing. The dynamics driving housing demand are likely to seem extremely different in various sections of the nation. It is difficult to draw generalizations about the elements that impact the demand for housing when we take into account aspects such as the socio-demographic status of each country (Uyar and Kılıç, 2017:293).

6. Using Reasons to Buy Real Estate

Real estate may be bought for a variety of purposes, the most common of which are usage, investment, rental, and use as a secondary house. Each of these can be broken down further into subcategories. In this specific circumstance, it is necessary to consider a variety of other factors, such as the amount of money required for rent each month and how easy it is to discover people seeking for rental properties (Lee and Yan, 2015:733). Housing acquisitions made by non-citizens of a country are influenced by many of the same variables as those made by nationals of that country; nevertheless, there are also a few significant differences to take into consideration that need to be taken into consideration. A non-native citizen's choice on the location of their future permanent residency is heavily influenced by the cultural and social structure of the country, as well as its degree of development, level of security, and political stability. Those who are not native speakers might carry out a variety of objectives via the purchase of real estate. *These actions may be categorized into the following five buckets: using property, holding property as a source of income, renting property, buying a residence permit, and becoming a citizen* (Bohle, 2014: 13). According to Demirli and Ayyıldırım (2016): 196, eliminating this restriction eliminates a significant barrier that Turkey must overcome. If we assemble the most relevant studies on the housing demand of foreigners found in the literature of research conducted overseas, we find that Barbu et al. (2017) places a strong emphasis on the link between House Price and House Price. Saiz (2007) did some study to find out how the housing market reacts when there are shocks caused by migration from other countries. According to a research that was conducted by Uyar and Kılıç (2017), the number of non-citizens who may live in a certain country is steadily growing. The authors Oztürk and Fitoz (2009) employed regression analysis as part of the framework for their study to investigate the factors that influence the supply and demand of housing. This was conducted as part of the scope of their job. The statistics support the conclusion that housing supply is one of the elements affecting liquidity expansion, per capita income, and housing prices. It is conceivable to draw the conclusion that housing supply is one of the factors deciding housing prices. The fact that one can get this outcome lends more credence to the likelihood that one can achieve this result. Between the years 1990 and 2006, Badurlar (2008) conducted research with the purpose of determining how the demand for housing in Turkey was affected by a variety of various macroeconomic variables.

7. Conclusion

The results of the study show that fluctuations in interest rates are the single most essential element to consider when attempting to explain the change in the demand for home loans. This has been shown to be the case. As was said in the prior sentence, the Central Bank Data Center is the organization that oversees producing these statistics (EVDS). The total number of homes bought by persons who were born in other countries will serve as the model's independent variable. The monthly average of the selling price said in dollars is one of the independent variables that are taken into consideration by the model. This is done in order to give the model a better chance of correctly predicting future sales. Assessments such as the Dickey Fuller (ADF), Philips-Perron, and Dickey Fuller are among the many different kinds that may be carried out (Yurdakul, 2000:23). In this investigation, the extended Dickey-Fuller (1981) and Phillips-Perron (1988) unit root tests were used to ascertain whether or not the information obtained throughout the research was stationary. In order to assess whether or not the data were steady, this step was taken. In a state of long-term equilibrium, co-integration is a method that may be used to investigate and determine whether or not there is a connection between the many economic variables being studied. Finding out whether or not there is a connection between the many economic indicators is one way to do this. In this method, the connection between components is analyzed, with the presumption being that they will eventually arrive at a state of long-term equilibrium with each other as a direct consequence of their interaction with one another. When individuals discuss the notion of cointegration, what they mean is that they are referring to the linear combination of nonstationary variables. This is what people mean when they say that cointegration is a concept. According to Goktaş (2005):115, the cointegration requirement needs the variables to be integrated with each other in the same order. This is because the order in which they are integrated determines the cointegration. The strategy that was suggested by Johansen (1988) is today acknowledged as one of the methodologies that has attained the maximum level of popularity among the population of people who are engaged in the practice of research. The Influence That Variability In Exchange Rates Have On Foreign Investors It is possible to say that the purchase rate decreases partially in the short term and again in the general average when the exchange rate decreases; when the exchange rate increases, it triggers the foreign investor to buy in the short term, considering the general average. Buying real estate from Turkey, when the selling prices are applied in TL, when the exchange rate increases (unless an equivalent increase is made based on TL rate), it causes the foreign investor to buy in the short term, considering the general average. If the sale prices are determined in foreign currency rather than in Turkish lira, then the fluctuation or increase in the exchange rate will have less of an effect in terms of sales to foreign investors.

This is because various regulations have been introduced to the use of foreign currency for precautionary purposes in our country. On the other hand, if there is a consistent and significant loss of value of the TL over the long run, this is one of the factors that will negatively affect the purchase made by the foreign investor over the long run. This is due to the belief that the investment will lose value over the long run when compared to the value of the foreign exchange.

8. References

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